

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea: Part XII. Heterochelates based on Bis 1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea Cobalt(III)

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A new series of heterochelates have been synthesised by the action of ortho-phenanthroline, α - α' -dipyridyl, glycine or ethylenediamine on the trans-diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt (III). A number of salts of the complex cations has been described. Molar conductance and equivalent weights of the chloride and sulphate salts respectively have been evaluated. All the complexes show two absorption bands, which are assigned to the transitions $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{1g}$ and $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{2g}$. The above ligands obey their usual position in the spectrochemical series i.e. O-phen $>$ dipy $>$ en $>$ glyH (where O-phen = ortho-phenanthroline, dipy = α - α' -dipyridyl, glyH = glycine and en = ethylenediamine).

Comprehensive studies have been undertaken in our Laboratory on the synthesis, characterisation and resolution of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(III). As a first phase of these investigations, researches have been carried out on bis-biguanide cobalt(III) and bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) moieties. Since results of such studies with ortho-phenanthroline bis biguanide cobalt(III), α - α' -dipyridyl bis biguanide cobalt(III), among others, have been extremely worthwhile^{1,2}, we planned similar studies with 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complexes.

TABLE I

Electrolytic conductance values at 33.5°

Complex	Dilution (litres)	64	128	256	512	1024	
1. [Co(o-phen) (AMUH) ₂] Cl ₃ .6H ₂ O	Λ^v	118.0	127.4	135.8	141.7	148.0	
	Λ^{∞}	148.6	150.8	153.3	154.6	157.5	
	Λ^{∞} (mean)	152.8	Ω^{-1}				
	Λ^M	458.4	$\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$				
		Equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution		Molar conductivity			
		Λ^{∞} (mean), Ω^{-1}		$\Lambda^M, \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$			
2. [Co (α - α' -dipy) (AMUH) ₂] Cl ₃ .7H ₂ O			146.1		438.3		
3. [Co (gly) (AMUH) ₂] Cl ₂ .5H ₂ O			142.9		285.8		
4. [Co (en) (AMUH) ₂] Cl ₃ . 2.5 H ₂ O			154.0		462.0		

Λ^{∞} was calculated from Λ^v from Walden formula $\Lambda^{\infty} = \Lambda^v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$ where n_1 is the valency of cation and n_2 is the valency of anion.

AMUH = 1-amidino-O-methylurea ; o-phen = ortho-phenanthroline ; α - α' -dipy = α - α' -dipyridyl ; glyH = glycine ; en = ethylenediamine.

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1. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 832.

2. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 842.

For bis-biguanide cobalt(III) heterochelates, cis-diammine bis biguanide cobalt(III) was found to be an ideal starting material for the synthetic route to the desired complexes. We had at our disposal the trans-diammine bis l-amidino-O-alkylurea, which was subjected to the action of various powerful bidentate ligands. Thus when trans-diammine bis l-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) is treated with ortho-phenanthroline, α - α' -dipyridyl etc. no evolution of ammonia was noticeable around room temperature. However, on raising the temperature to around 60-70° on a steam bath, evolution of ammonia was there and the desired heterochelates were formed. Thus trans to cis isomerisation occurred in the presence of the above bidentates and especially on warming to a higher temperature. Unlike the corresponding heterochelates containing biguanide, the complexes are extremely soluble in water, so that in many cases crystallisation had to be made by repeated scratching with acetone. The salts with optically active anions, such as d-tartrate or d-camphor sulphonate appeared to be too soluble, so that our desire to separate the optical isomers remained unfulfilled. Conductance measurements with the chloride salts of the different cations were completed at different dilutions and therefrom the mean equivalent conductance at infinite dilution and thus the molar conductance calculated.

TABLE II

Equivalent weight values

Complex	Found	Required*
1. [Co (<i>o</i> -phen) (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 5H ₂ O	230	235
2. [Co (α - α' dipy) (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 2H ₂ O	202	209
3. [Co (gly) (AMUH) ₂](SO ₄)	225	230
4. [Co (en) (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} 5H ₂ O	189	195

*These values have been deduced on the basis of elemental analysis and conductance measurements.

The values have an upward trend compared to the usual range of tri-univalent ions or bi-univalent ions³. This is because of a high temperature existing at the time of the measurements. These values, however, agree well with those already reported for comparable series of the bis-biguanide cobalt(III) complexes^{1,2}. The equivalent weights of the above salts have also been determined by the simple cation exchange technique and once again these agree well with values deduced from the analytical and conductance data.

The absorption spectra recorded over the wavelength range 320 m μ to 550 m μ , as usual reveal two ligand field bands representing the transitions $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{1g}$ and $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{2g}$. A comparison of the corresponding bands gives a qualitative ligand field order. This is readily followed from the frequency shift of both the long and short wavelength bands. This is also the order the above ligands are situated in the spectrochemical series^{4,5}. For drawing a further comparative ligand field strength of the l-amidino-O-alkylureas, the complex tris l-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) sulphate

3. M. M. Jones, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice Hall, 1964, p-254.

4. C. K. Jorgensen, "Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding", Pergamon Press, 1962, p-109.

5. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1962, p-579.

was prepared and its spectra recorded. This reveals a very close ligand field strength of the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea and ethylenediamine so that we have the following order :

TABLE III

Electronic absorption spectral studies

Complex	Band II		Band I	
	Wave number cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity $\text{litre mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Wave number cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity $\text{litre mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
1. $[\text{Co}(\text{o-phen})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	30,000	16.00	21,300— 21,000	146
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{o-o'-dipy})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	„	1550	21,300- 21,000	176
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{gly})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}_2$	28,600- 28,200	214	19,800	131
4. $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	28,600- 28,200	182	20,800	160
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{APiUH})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	29,000- 27,800	192	20,600	180

APiUH=1-amidino-O-isopropylurea

In this report we have used 1-amidino-O-methylurea as a representative of the class of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas. It is our impression that using the other heavier members of the series enhances further the solubility of the heterochelates, making the programme of isolation and purification more tedious.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-amidino-O-methylurea, 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea sulphates were prepared and purified according to the published procedure^{6,7}. trans-diammine bis-1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono sulphate and mono chloride were prepared according to the method described earlier.⁷ Sodium cobaltinitrite was prepared according to the method described elsewhere⁸.

The complexes described below are highly soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and acetone. The iodide salts have reasonable solubility both in water and alcohol. Unless otherwise mentioned all the complexes were dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 .

1. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate*. Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono sulphate (1.0 g) and ortho-phenanthroline monohydrate (0.5 g) were mixed with water (20 ml) and heated on a steam bath for about one hour until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The dark red solution was cooled and

6. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499.

7. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, this series Part IX. 1968, **45**, 115.

8. W. G. Palmer, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, 1959, p-549.

neutralised with 2N H_2SO_4 . To this solution rectified spirit was added in the cold with stirring. The rose red crystals separated were filtered off and washed with spirit. $\{Found: Co, 8.5; N, 20.2; SO_4, 19.9; H_2O (by\ loss\ at\ 110^\circ), 13.2. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] (SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 5H_2O$ requires Co, 8.3; N, 19.9; $SO_4, 20.4; H_2O, 12.8\%$.

2. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride*. Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono chloride and ortho-phenanthroline monohydrate (0.5 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath until evolution of ammonia ceased. The dark red solution was concentrated, neutralised with dilute HCl and cooled in ice. The rose red crystals separated were filtered off and washed with spirit. Addition of spirit to the filtrate gave more crystals. $\{Found: Co, 8.8; N, 20.46; Cl, 15.1; H_2O (by\ loss\ at\ 110^\circ), 15.9. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] Cl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ requires Co, 8.6; N, 20.49; Cl, 15.5; $H_2O, 15.8\%$.

3. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) iodide*. To the dark red solution of the chloride, as obtained above, was added a concentrated solution of KI and cooled in ice for few hours. The brown crystals separated were filtered and washed with ice cold water. $\{Found: Co, 7.1; N, 16.1; I, 45.4. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] I_3$ requires Co, 6.9; N, 16.4; I, 45.0%.

4. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chromate*. To the dark red solution of the chloride was added a concentrated solution of K_2CrO_4 and cooled in the frigidaire for 2 days. The yellow crystals formed were filtered and washed with spirit. $\{Found: Cr, 12.3; N, 21.4. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] (CrO_4)_{1.5}$ requires Cr, 12.1; N, 21.7%.

5. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride-d-tartrate*. The dark red solution of the chloride after evolution of ammonia ceased was treated with calculated amount of d-tartaric acid and evaporated to a small volume. The mixture was cooled and rose red crystals were obtained by scratching with acetone. $\{Found: Co, 7.8; N, 17.22; Cl, 4.2; H_2O (by\ loss\ at\ 110^\circ), 17.7. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] Cl \cdot d-tartrate. 8H_2O$ requires Co, 7.5; N, 17.5; Cl, 4.4; $H_2O, 18.0\%$.

6. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) d-camphor-10-sulphonate* was prepared as rose red crystals similarly as the chloride-d-tartrate but a calculated amount of neutralised d-camphor-10-sulphonic acid was added instead of d-tartaric acid. $\{Found: Co, 5.3; N, 12.4. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] (CS)_3$ requires Co, 5.0; N, 12.0%.

7. *Ortho-phenanthroline bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite* was prepared by double decomposition of the sulphate with a concentrated solution of $Na_3[Co(NO_2)_6]$. The yellow crystals formed were filtered and washed with spirit. $\{Found: Co, 13.5; N, 25.7; H_2O (by\ loss\ at\ 110^\circ), 8.4. [Co(O-phen) (AMUH)_2] [Co(NO_2)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Co, 13.4; N, 25.5; $H_2O, 8.2\%$.

8. $\alpha-\alpha'$ -Dipyridyl bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate. Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate (1 g) and $\alpha-\alpha'$ -dipyridyl (0.4 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath until all the ammonia evolved. This was then treated similarly as the ortho-phenanthroline derivative. The substance is rose red in colour. $\{Found: Co, 9.6; N, 22.5; SO_4, 23.1. [Co(\alpha-\alpha'-dipy)(AMUH)_2] (SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Co, 9.4; N, 22.4; $SO_4, 23.0\%$.

9. α - α' -Dipyridyl bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride was prepared as for the ortho-phenanthroline derivative using α - α' -dipyridyl (0.39 g). This is rose red. $\{$ Found: Co, 8.9; N, 21.4; Cl, 15.3; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 19.0. [Co α - α' -dipy] (AMUH)₂] Cl₃·7H₂O requires Co, 8.7; N, 15.5; H₂O, 18.5% $\}$.

10. α - α' -Dipyridyl bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) iodide was prepared as for the iodide salt of the ortho-phenanthroline complex. This is rose red. $\{$ Found: Co, 7.3; N, 17.2; I, 45.8. [Co (α - α' -dipy) (AMUH)₂] I₃ requires Co, 7.1; N, 16.9; I, 46.0% $\}$.

11. α - α' -Dipyridyl bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite was prepared as yellow crystals by double decomposition of the sulphate with a concentrated solution of Na₃[Co(NO₂)₆]. $\{$ Found: Co, 14.0; N, 26.0. [Co (α - α' -dipy) (AMUH)₂] [Co(NO₂)₆] requires Co, 13.8; N, 26.2% $\}$.

12. Glycine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate.—Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono sulphate (1g) and glycine (0.18 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath for about one hour until evolution of ammonia ceased. The colour of the solution changed from rose to violet. The solution was cooled and neutralised with 2N H₂SO₄. Addition of acetone to this solution produced an oily layer from which violet crystals were obtained by the addition of more acetone followed by scratching. The mass was dissolved in minimum amount of water and again treated with acetone and scratched to obtain the pure material. This was filtered and washed with acetone. $\{$ Found: Co, 12.8; N, 27.0; SO₄, 20.5. [Co(gly) (AMUH)₂] SO₄ requires Co, 12.8; N, 27.4; SO₄, 20.9% $\}$.

13. Glycine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride. Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono chloride (1g) and glycine (0.18 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath until the evolution of ammonia ceased. This was then treated as for the ortho-phenanthroline compound. $\{$ Found: Co, 11.0; N, 25.0; Cl, 13.0; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 17.4. [Co (gly) (AMUH)₂] Cl₂·5H₂O requires Co, 11.2; N, 24.6; Cl, 13.4; H₂O, 17.1% $\}$.

14. Glycine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) iodide was prepared as brownish red crystals by following a similar procedure as for the corresponding ortho-phenanthroline compound. $\{$ Found: Co, 9.6; N, 20.4; I, 41.4. [Co(gly) (AMUH)₂] I₂ requires Co, 9.5; N, 20.3; I, 41.0% $\}$.

15. Glycine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite was prepared as yellow crystals by double decomposition of the sulphate with a concentrated solution of Na₃ [Co(NO₂)₆]. $\{$ Found: Co, 17.0; N, 30.8. [Co (gly) (AMUH)₂]₃·[Co(NO₂)₆] requires Co, 16.7; N, 31.0% $\}$.

16. Ethylenediamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate. Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate (1 g) and ethylenediamine (0.15 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath for about one hour until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The dark red solution was then cooled, neutralised with 2N H₂SO₄ and cooled in an ice bath for 3 hr. The orange crystals separated were filtered and washed with spirit. $\{$ Found: Co, 10.2; N, 23.6; SO₄, 24.5; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 15.4 [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] (SO₄)_{1.5}·5H₂O requires Co, 10.0; N, 23.9; SO₄, 24.6; H₂O, 15.3% $\}$.

17. *Ethylenediamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride* was prepared as for the ortho-phenanthroline complex using ethylenediamine (0.15 g). The substance is shining orange. {Found: Co, 11.9; N, 28.1; Cl, 21.4; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 8.4. [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] Cl₃·2.5H₂O requires Co, 11.7; N, 27.9; Cl, 21.3; H₂O, 8.9%}.

The iodide and bromide salts were prepared by metathetic reaction of the chloride with a concentrated solution of KI and KBr respectively.

18. *Ethylenediamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) iodide* is rose red. {Found: Co, 7.3; N, 16.8; I, 47.0; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 11.4. [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] I₃·5H₂O requires Co, 7.1; N, 17.0; I, 46.4; H₂O, 10.9%}.

19. *Ethylenediamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) bromide* is rose red. {Found: Co, 9.8; N, 23.1; Br, 39.7. [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] Br₃·H₂O requires Co, 9.6; N, 23.0; Br, 39.4%}.

20. *Ethylenediamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride-d tartrate*: Diamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono chloride (1 g) and ethylenediamine (0.15 g) were heated on a steam bath until the evolution of ammonia ceased. This was then treated as for the corresponding ortho-phenanthroline compound. {Found: Co, 8.7; N, 20.4; Cl, 5.2; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 22.6. [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] Cl·d-tartrate·9H₂O requires Co, 8.4; N, 20.1; H₂O, 23.2%}.

21. *Ethylenediamine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) nitrite*: trans-Dinitro bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) nitrite⁹ and ethylenediamine (1:1 ratio) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath for one hour. This was then cooled in ice bath for one hour to give shining rose red crystals, which were filtered and washed with spirit. {Found: Co, 10.7; N, 32.2. [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] (NO₂)₃·4H₂O requires Co, 10.5; N, 32.4%}.

22. *Ethylenediamine-bis-1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) cobaltinitrite* was obtained as orange crystals by double decomposition of the sulphate with a concentrated solution of Na₃ [Co(NO₂)₆]. {Found: Co, 15.35; N, 29.2; [Co(en) (AMUH)₂] [Co(NO₂)₆]·4.5 H₂O requires Co, 15.42; N, 29.2%}.

23. *tris-1-amidino-O-isopropylurea cobalt(III) sulphate*. CoSO₄·7H₂O (1.2 g) and 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea sulphate (4.0 g) were dissolved in water (20 ml). The solution was made alkaline by addition of dilute NaOH. The yellow cobaltous complex formed was oxidised by H₂O₂ (20 vol., 5 ml). A current of air was then passed through the resulting solution for half an hour. This was then filtered, neutralised with dilute H₂SO₄ and cooled in ice for one hour. The rose red crystals separated out were filtered, washed first with ice cold water and then with spirit and dried in air. {Found: Co, 8.7; N, 24.9; SO₄, 21.5; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 6.5. [Co (AP¹UH)₃] (SO)₄·1.5·2.5H₂O, requires Co, 8.6; N, 24.7; SO₄, 21.1; H₂O 6.6%}.

The experimental procedures were similar to those described in Part IX of this series.

This is a pleasure to acknowledge our indebtedness to C.S.I.R. for financial assistance to one of us (A.S.). We express our gratitude to Prof. Santi Ranjan Palit for his interest

in our scheme. We also thank Prof S. K. Siddhanta for the encouragement given us. We gratefully acknowledge the generous gift of dicyandiamide by the American Cyanamide Company and of ortho-phenanthroline and 2-2' -dipyridyl by G. Frederic Smith Chemical Company. We record with appreciation the services received from Mr. M. Sadhu while setting up the semimicro Duma combustion train.

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Received, May 16, 1966.